

Studies on Some Metal Complexes of 4,6-Dihydroxycoumaran-3-one

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4,6-Dihydroxycoumaran-3-one gives colour reactions with a number of metal ions on paper chromatograms. Solid complexes of the ligand with V(IV), Cr(III), Mn(II), Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zr(IV), Th(IV) and U(VI) transition metal ions were prepared and investigated using infra-red and electronic spectroscopy and thermal and elemental analysis. The results suggest the following formulations for the various complexes. ML_2 , where $M = VO(II)$, $Cu(II)$ and $Ni(II)$; $M'L_2 \cdot 2C_2H_5OH$, where $M' = Mn(II)$, $Co(II)$ and $UO_2(II)$; $M''L_3$, where $M'' = Cr(III)$ and $Fe(III)$; ThL_4 and $ZrL_2 \cdot 2C_2H_5OH \cdot Cl_2$.

A number of complexes of β -hydroxy coumarones are known in literature¹⁻¹⁰, however, no work has been done on the metal complexes of 4,6-dihydroxycoumaran-3-one (Fig. 1). In this ligand the carbonyl is hydrogen bonded to the hydroxyl as shown by its infra-red spectrum $\nu C=O$ (1710 cm^{-1}) appears at 1670 cm^{-1} while $\nu O-H$ (normal $\sim 3650\text{ cm}^{-1}$) appears at 3520 cm^{-1} . Further the hydroxyl at position 4 being highly acidic leads to the formation of the anion with relative ease. The compound is thus expected to act as strong chelating ligand.

Fig. 1

Experimental

4,6-Dihydroxycoumaran-3-one was prepared by Hoesch reaction between phloroglucinol (60g) and chloroacetonitrile in dry ether in the presence of dry HCl and anhydrous $ZnCl_2$ at 0° . The product ω -chlorophloroacetophenone (40g) was refluxed with sodium acetate (60g) for five hours to give 4,6-dihydroxycoumaran-3-one¹¹. It is purified by repeated crystallization from water, yield 22g, m.p. 254° (lit.¹¹ $254-255^\circ$). The metal complexes were prepared by mixing the metal ion and the ligand in stoichiometric ratio of 1 : 10 (M:L) in ethanol and refluxed on a water bath for one hour. The ligand to metal ratio was kept relatively high to provide for any high coordination number of metal ions. The pH range for precipitation was found to be 5.2 to 5.6. The complexes were repeatedly washed with acetone to remove the excess of the ligand. They were recrystallized from alcohol and dried in vacuum over anhydrous calcium chloride.

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The infra-red spectra of the ligand and the complexes were recorded on a Perkin Elmer instrument for the region 4000 to 400 cm^{-1} . Electronic absorption spectra of the complexes was recorded as diffuse reflectance spectra on VSU20 Carl Zeiss spectrophotometer and the elemental analysis for C and H and metal contents were carried out by the usual known methods. The TG curves of the complexes were obtained on the thermobalance (F.C.1., Sindri) and the DTA curves were obtained on DTA-02 Universal apparatus at the heating rate of $10^\circ/\text{min}$.

Results and Discussion

On the basis of results of elemental analysis for C, H and metal contents (Table 1) the following formulations are proposed for the complex. $[VO(C_8H_5O_4)_2]$; $[Cr(C_8H_5O_4)_3]$; $[Mn(C_8H_5O_4)_2 \cdot 2C_2H_5OH]$; $[Fe(C_8H_5O_4)_3]$; $[Co(C_8H_5O_4)_2 \cdot 2C_2H_5OH]$; $[Ni(C_8H_5O_4)_2]$; $[Cu(C_8H_5O_4)_2]$; $[Zr(C_8H_5O_4)_2 \cdot 2C_2H_5OH]Cl_2$; $[UO_2(C_8H_5O_4)_2 \cdot 2C_2H_5OH]$ and $[Th(C_8H_5O_4)_4]$.

The infra-red spectrum of the ligand and the complexes (Table 2) support the above formulations proposed for these complexes. The infra-red spectra of the complexes when compared with the corresponding spectrum of the ligand show shifts in principal bands, due to the $\nu(O-H)$, $\nu(C=O)$ and $\nu(O-C)$ stretching modes which occur at 3520 , 1670 and 1070 cm^{-1} in the ligand. Table (2) shows that the $\nu(O-H)$ stretching mode appears at lower frequencies in the complexes ranging from $3280-3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Similarly the $\nu(C=O)$ frequency (1670 cm^{-1}) also gets shifted to much lower values between $1610-1620\text{ cm}^{-1}$, thereby confirming the coordination of the metal ions through the oxygens of the hydroxyl and the carbonyl group. In addition new bands appear as a result of the $\nu(M-O)$ or $\nu(M-O+C-C)$ stretching modes. These vibrational

TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS (%)

S. No.	Complexes	Colour	Calculated			Found		
			C	H	M	C	H	M
1.	VO(C ₈ H ₅ O ₄) ₂	Yellow	48.36	2.5	12.84	48.0	2.8	13.0
2.	Cr(C ₈ H ₅ O ₄) ₃	Red	52.65	2.47	9.58	53.3	3.2	10.0
3.	Mn(C ₈ H ₅ O ₄) ₂ ·2C ₂ H ₅ OH	Yellow	50.14	4.5	11.48	50.5	4.0	12.0
4.	Fe(C ₈ H ₅ O ₄) ₃	Purple	52.80	2.72	10.13	53.1	2.5	10.6
5.	Co(C ₈ H ₅ O ₄) ₂ ·2C ₂ H ₅ OH	Pink	49.80	4.5	12.26	48.9	4.0	12.5
6.	Ni(C ₈ H ₅ O ₄) ₂	Pink	49.39	2.5	15.10	49.9	3.1	15.6
7.	Cu(C ₈ H ₅ O ₄) ₂	Red	48.79	2.54	16.01	48.3	2.3	10.5
8.	Zr(C ₈ H ₅ O ₄) ₂ ·2C ₂ H ₅ OHCl ₂ *	Pink	41.88	3.76	15.7	42.0	3.5	15.9
9.	UO ₂ (C ₈ H ₅ O ₄) ₂ ·2C ₂ H ₅ OH	Yellow	38.76	2.8	38.5	39.0	3.0	39.0
10.	Th(C ₈ H ₅ O ₄) ₄	Brown	43.84	2.24	26.0	45.0	2.5	26.5

*Cl calculated 12.04 ; Found 12.8

TABLE 2—PRINCIPAL BANDS (cm⁻¹) IN THE IR SPECTRA

S. No.	Complex	ν(O-H)	ν(C=O)	ν(O-C)	ν(M—O) or (M—O+C—C)
1.	C ₈ H ₅ O ₄	3520	1670	1070	-
2.	VO(C ₈ H ₅ O ₄) ₂	3320	1610	1080	965,530
3.	Cr(C ₈ H ₅ O ₄) ₃	3400	1620	1080	500,475
4.	Mn(C ₈ H ₅ O ₄) ₂ ·2C ₂ H ₅ OH	3400	1600	1080	450
5.	Fe(C ₈ H ₅ O ₄) ₃	3420	1620	1090	430
6.	Co(C ₈ H ₅ O ₄) ₂ ·2C ₂ H ₅ OH	3350	1615	1080	450
7.	Ni(C ₈ H ₅ O ₄) ₂	3280	1620	1080	440,615
8.	Cu(C ₈ H ₅ O ₄) ₂	3400	1600	1080	430
9.	Zr(C ₈ H ₅ O ₄) ₂ ·2EtOH·Cl ₂	3400	1600	1080	450
10.	UO ₂ (C ₈ H ₅ O ₄) ₂ ·2EtOH	3380	1610	1050	1150,825,700
11.	Th(C ₈ H ₅ O ₄) ₄	3420	1600	1075	460

modes appear at 965, 330 cm⁻¹ in V(IV), 500, 475 cm⁻¹ in the Cr(III), 450 cm⁻¹ in the Mn(II), 430 cm⁻¹ in Fe(III), 450 cm⁻¹ in Co(II), 440 and 615 cm⁻¹ in Ni(II), 430 cm⁻¹ in Cu(II), 450 cm⁻¹ in Zr(IV), 1150, 825 and 700 cm⁻¹ in U(VI) and 460 cm⁻¹ in the Th(IV) complexes. The infra-red spectra of the complexes thus unambiguously confirm the formation of the complexes and the donor sites in the ligand^{1,2-15}.

The electronic absorption spectra of the complexes further elucidate the nature and the configuration of the complexes. The bands at 33333, 20000 and 12500 cm⁻¹ are assigned to ²A₁←²B₂, ²B₁←²B₂ and ³E₂←³B₂ transitions as is obtained in the square pyramidal complexes of VO²⁺ ion¹⁶. The octahedral geometry of the Cr(III) complexes is confirmed by the transitions from ⁴A_{2g} to ⁴T_{1g}(P), ⁴T_{1g}(F) and ⁴T_{2g} arising at 41666, 2871 and 18867 cm⁻¹¹⁷. The [Mn(C₈H₅O₄)₂·2C₂H₅OH] complex shows bands at 26566, 20000 and 17241 which are assigned to ⁴T_{2g}(D)←⁶A_{1g}, ⁴T_{2g}←⁶A_{1g} and ⁴T_{1g}←⁶A_{1g} transition confirming octahedral configuration of the complex. Similarly the octahedral Fe(III) complex being octahedral shows the transitions from ⁶A_{1g} to ⁴T_{1g}, ⁴E_g, and ⁴T_{2g} at 31258, 27827 and 19047 cm⁻¹ respectively. The Ni(C₈H₅O₄)₂ complex is assigned a square planar geometry because no transition is found below 10000 cm⁻¹ and the bands at 18181, 25000 and 28571 cm⁻¹ are assigned to ν₁, ν₂ and ν₃ transitions in the square planar field. Cu(C₈H₅O₄)₂ has band at 18181 cm⁻¹, indicative of the distorted square planar nature of the complex.

The Zr(IV) complex [Zr(C₈H₅O₄)₂·2C₂H₅OH]Cl₂ has bands at 43487, 31746, 25000 and 19238 cm⁻¹. These bands are assigned to charge transfer transitions on account of electronic transitions within the ligand, metal ligand and ligand to metal electron transfer^{20,21}. The information conveyed by electronic absorption spectra is of limited scope in this case.

The Uranium(VI) complex [UO₂(C₈H₅O₄)₂·2C₂H₅OH] and Th(IV) complex Th(C₈H₅O₄)₄ show bands at 40816, 25000 and 20000, 43478, 29411 and 19847 cm⁻¹ respectively; U(VI) and Th(IV) with 5f⁰ electronic configuration have no 5f→5f or 5f→6d transitions²². The appearance of bands in their electronic spectra can obviously be assigned to electron transfer bands.

The chemical composition and the structures proposed on the basis of infra-red, electronic and elemental analysis are further supported by thermal analysis of the complexes (Table 3). The TG curves of Mn(II), Co(II), Zr(IV) and UO₂(II) complexes show two distinct steps due to the progressive loss of two ethanol molecules. The percent loss in mass is in conformity with the suggested decompositions. The DTA in all these complexes show a single endotherm in the region of the loss of two ethanol molecules. The TG curves of Fe(III), Cr(III), V(IV), Cu(II), Ni(II) and Th(IV) complexes do not show any change in the weight loss upto 120°, suggestive of the absence of any coordinated ethanol molecules in them. The decomposition at higher temperature is

TABLE 3—TGA LOSS IN MASS PERCENT

S. No.	Complex	Calculated			Found		
		1st step	Ind step	Final product	1st step	Ind step	Final product
1.	VO(C ₈ H ₅ O ₄) ₂	-	-	77.90	-	-	76.9
2.	Cr(C ₈ H ₅ O ₄) ₃	-	-	72.0	-	-	73.0
3.	Mn(C ₈ H ₅ O ₄) ₂ .2C ₂ H ₅ OH	9.6	19.2	74.4	-	19.0	75.0
4.	Fe(C ₈ H ₅ O ₄) ₃	-	-	85.6	-	-	85.0
5.	Co(C ₈ H ₅ O ₄) ₂ .C ₂ H ₅ OH	9.4	18.9	84.5	10.0	20.0	85.5
6.	Ni(C ₈ H ₅ O ₄) ₂	-	-	81.9	-	-	80.1
7.	Cu(C ₈ H ₅ O ₄) ₂	-	-	83.6	-	-	82.2
8.	Zr(C ₈ H ₅ O ₄) ₂ .2C ₂ H ₅ OH.Cl ₂	7.77	15.7	78.2	8.5	16.1	78.9
9.	UO ₂ (C ₈ H ₅ O ₄) ₂ .2C ₂ H ₅ OH	5.9	11.8	64.2	-	12.2	65.0
10.	Th(C ₈ H ₅ O ₄) ₄	-	-	70.4	-	-	72.0

continuous and a single broad endotherm is obtained. No intermediates could be isolated and characterized because of their unstable nature. The final products in all the cases are the corresponding metal oxides i.e., VO₂, CrO₃, MnO, Fe₂O₃, CoO, NiO, CuO, ZrO₂, ThO₂ and U₃O₈. This is confirmed by the calculated weights of these oxides.

From the foregoing discussion it is clear that the infra-red and electronic spectral and thermal analysis studies support the formulations for the complexes. The following tentative structures for these complexes are proposed (Fig 2).

Fig. 2

Where M = Fe(III), Cr(III); n = 3 and m = 0
 M = Ni(II), Cu(I), V(II); n = 2 and m = 0
 M = Mn(II), Co(II), Zr(IV), UO₂(VI);
 n = 2 and m = 2
 and M = Th(IV): n = 4 and m = 0.

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